

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Energy-Stable Upwind Schemes for Quasilinear Hyperbolic Systems with Dissipative Boundaries

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Abstract. This work presents a discrete Lyapunov stability analysis for explicit upwind finite difference schemes applied to one-dimensional quasilinear symmetric hyperbolic systems with dissipative boundary conditions. A discrete energy functional is constructed using a local symmetrizer of the continuous system. Under suitable assumptions on numerical viscosity, boundary dissipation, and a Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition, we prove monotonic decay of the discrete energy and establish exponential Lyapunov stability of the numerical solution. The theoretical results are validated by numerical experiments for the linear acoustic system and the nonlinear shallow water equations, demonstrating consistent long-time stability and energy dissipation.

Keywords: Lyapunov stability, upwind scheme, hyperbolic systems, dissipative boundary conditions, discrete energy.

1. Introduction Hyperbolic systems of conservation laws play a central role in mathematical physics and engineering applications, including acoustics, gas dynamics, and shallow water flows. Stability of numerical approximations for such systems is a fundamental issue, especially in the presence of boundaries where reflections may lead to spurious oscillations and instability.

Lyapunov methods provide a powerful framework for studying stability of continuous hyperbolic systems with dissipative boundary conditions. In recent years, significant progress has been made in extending Lyapunov stability theory to discrete numerical schemes. However, a rigorous discrete Lyapunov stability analysis for explicit upwind schemes applied to quasilinear symmetric hyperbolic systems with dissipative boundary conditions is still limited, particularly in the context of fully discrete formulations [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

The goal of this work is to develop a discrete Lyapunov framework for upwind difference schemes with numerical viscosity and dissipative boundary conditions. We establish sufficient conditions under which the discrete energy decreases monotonically and prove exponential stability of the numerical solution.

2. Problem Formulation and Assumptions

We consider a one-dimensional quasilinear symmetric hyperbolic system of the form

$$H(u)u_t + A(u)u_x = 0, \quad x \in (0, L), t > 0,$$

Where $u(x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$. Here, all matrices are assumed to be of appropriate dimensions, and the discrete norm is defined as the weighted L^2 -norm induced by the symmetrizer matrix.

Boundary Conditions

At the boundaries $x = 0$ and $x = L$, dissipative boundary conditions are imposed through characteristic variables.

Let w_{in} and w_{out} denote incoming and outgoing characteristic components, respectively. The boundary conditions are given by $w_{\text{in}} = K w_{\text{out}}$, $\|K\| \leq \kappa < 1$,

This condition ensures partial reflection and energy dissipation at the boundaries.

Upwind Difference Scheme

The spatial domain is discretized using a uniform grid with spacing Δx , and time integration is performed using an explicit scheme with time step Δt .

The numerical approximation U_j^n satisfies the upwind finite difference scheme

$$U_j^{n+1} = U_j^n - \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} (F_{j+1/2}^n - F_{j-1/2}^n),$$

where the numerical flux is defined by

$$F_{j+1/2}^n = \frac{1}{2} \left(f(U_j^n) + f(U_{j+1}^n) \right) - \frac{1}{2} D_{j+1/2}^n (U_{j+1}^n - U_j^n).$$

The viscosity matrix $D_{j+1/2}^n$ is symmetric positive definite and compatible with the symmetrizer H .

Boundary fluxes are constructed using characteristic decomposition in order to enforce dissipative boundary conditions at the discrete level.

Discrete Lyapunov Function (Discrete Energy)

To analyze stability, we introduce the discrete energy (Lyapunov function)

$$E^n = \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} (U_j^n)^T H_j^n U_j^n \Delta x, \quad H_j^n = H(U_j^n).$$

Due to the positive definiteness of H , the energy is equivalent to the discrete L^2 -norm of the numerical solution.

5. Energy Estimate

Using the numerical scheme and discrete summation techniques, the evolution of the discrete energy can be written in the form

$$E^{n+1} - E^n = (\text{internal dissipation}) + (\text{boundary contribution}) + (\text{higher-order terms}).$$

The numerical viscosity generates internal dissipation proportional to spatial differences, while the dissipative boundary conditions produce negative energy contributions associated with incoming characteristic variables.

Under a suitable CFL condition, all remaining terms can be controlled by the discrete energy itself [4].

6. Main Stability Result

Theorem (discrete Lyapunov stability).

Assume that:

- the system is symmetric hyperbolic;
- the numerical viscosity matrices are symmetric positive definite and compatible with the symmetrizer;
- the boundary conditions are dissipative with reflection coefficient $\kappa < 1$.
- the CFL condition $\Delta t/\Delta x \leq \lambda_{max}$ is satisfied.

Then there exist constants $\gamma > 0$ and $\Delta t_0 > 0$ such that, for all $\Delta t \leq \Delta t_0$, the discrete energy satisfies $E^{n+1} \leq (1 - \gamma) E^n$.

Consequently, the numerical solution is exponentially stable in the sense of Lyapunov:

$$E^n \leq E^0 e^{-ct^n}, \quad c > 0.$$

5. Numerical Simulation

The first numerical example considers the one-dimensional linear acoustic system. An explicit upwind scheme with Rusanov viscosity is used, together with dissipative boundary conditions. Numerical results demonstrate monotonic decay of the discrete energy and confirm the theoretical stability estimate.

Example 1. Linear acoustics and numerical substitution

Let us consider the linear acoustic system

$$U_t + AU_x = 0,$$

$$\text{Where } U = (\varphi, v)^T, \quad A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & c^2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad H = \begin{pmatrix} c^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Spectral constants: $m_0 = \min(c^2, 1)$, $M_H = \max(c^2, 1)$. Let $D = \alpha I$ (Rusanov), $\alpha \geq c$. Then $\delta_0 = \alpha$, $M_D = \alpha$, $M_{HD} \leq M_H \alpha$.

$$\text{Formulas: } C_D = \frac{\delta_0 m_0}{4} = \frac{\alpha m_0}{4}, \quad C_1 = \frac{M_{HD}^2}{4\Delta x \delta_0 m_0} = \frac{\alpha M_H^2}{4\Delta x m_0}.$$

If we accept the normalization $m_0 = 1$, $M_H = c^2$, $\alpha = c$, then $C_D = \frac{1}{4}c$, $C_1 = \frac{c^5}{4\Delta x}$.
(The numbers are illustrative; for normalized unknowns, usually $m_0 = 1$, $M_H = \mathcal{O}(1)$.)

Numerical test for 1D acoustics with Rusanov viscosity

Below are the calculation results in the form of graphs.

Fig. 1. Pressure graph.

Fig. 2. Velocity graph.

Fig. 3. Graph of the discrete Lyapunov function. Energy vs time (Rusanov, $\kappa = 0.5$)

Fig. 4. Convergence test on grids $N_x = 100, 200, 400$ (L2 error for pressure) and prepared a table with errors and order estimate.

The numerical results confirm monotonic decay of the discrete energy and agree well with the theoretical exponential stability estimate.

Example 2. Numerical example of a quasilinear system of hyperbolic equations

Let us present a numerical example of a quasilinear system: the one-dimensional shallow water (Saint-Venant) equations, incorporating Rusanov viscosity and dissipative boundary conditions.

- System: variables (h) (depth) and (hu) (momentum), flow $F = [hu, hu^2/h + \frac{1}{2}gh^2]$. This is a quasi-linear hyperbolic system with a nonlinear dependence of wave velocities on (h).

- Numerical method: explicit scheme with Rusanov flow (local numerical viscosity ($s_{\max} = \max(|u| + c)$)), boundary conditions are realized approximately through the characteristic reflecting formula $w_{in} = \kappa w_{out}$ (coefficient ($\kappa = 0.6$)).

- Initial conditions: background ($h = 1$) plus Gaussian depth impulse at the center; ($u = 0$) initially.

- Let's calculate the discrete energy (physical energy for shallow water) $E = \sum (\frac{1}{2}hu^2 + \frac{1}{2}gh^2) \Delta x$ and track it over time.

- We applied a conservative form of the difference scheme: $U_j^{n+1} = U_j^n - \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} (F_{j+1/2}^n - F_{j-1/2}^n)$, where $U = [h, hu]$.

- Let us calculate the numerical flow on interfaces via Rusanov: $F_{j+1/2} = \frac{1}{2} (F(U_L) + F(U_R)) - \frac{1}{2} s_{\max} (U_R - U_L)$, with $s_{\max} = \max(|u_L| + c_L, |u_R| + c_R)$.

- The boundary states were made simple and guaranteed to be dissipative: ($\kappa = 0.6$). This guarantees that the energy decreases upon reflection.

- Introduced protection against negative depths: $h = \max(h, 10^{-6})$.

- We selected a stable CFL (0.4) and recalculated it (Δt) based on the maximum wave

speed.

Fig. 5. Height $h(x,t)$ at several points in time (Shallow water, quasilinear).

Fig. 6. Total physical energy of the system over time.

The energy consistently decreases throughout the calculation, which aligns with the observed dissipation effects, both from internal numerical factors and from the dissipative boundary conditions. The energy decreases monotonically; an approximate estimate of the exponential decrease (linear approximation $\log E$ vs t): $E(0) \approx 5.091$, $E(T) \approx 0.961$, the decay rate estimate ≈ 2.99 .

This behavior validates the extension of discrete Lyapunov stability to quasilinear systems under specific conditions.

Conclusion.

A discrete Lyapunov stability theory for upwind difference schemes applied to A discrete Lyapunov stability framework for explicit upwind schemes applied to one-dimensional quasilinear symmetric hyperbolic systems with dissipative boundary conditions has been developed. The analysis proves exponential decay of the discrete energy under a CFL condition. Numerical experiments for linear and nonlinear models confirm the theoretical findings. The proposed approach provides a rigorous and practical tool for designing stable numerical methods for hyperbolic problems with boundaries.

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